

TECHNOLOGY OF CONDUCTING PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES WITH THE USE OF MODERN NON-TRADITIONAL TYPES OF HEALTH RELATED PHYSICAL CULTURE

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Abstract

Rapidly developing modern society is interested in a healthy competitive younger generation. However, the health of young people is constantly deteriorating.

This article was presented an analysis of the physical development and physical fitness of students living in environmentally unfavorable environmental conditions, and also experimentally tested a program that includes modern non-traditional types of health physical culture, which contributes to health promotion, improvement of physical fitness, and improvement of the effectiveness of physical education classes for students with a predisposition to diseases.

Keywords: ecology, health, student youth, physical development, physical fitness, morphological and functional indicators, predisposition to diseases, computer electro-acupuncture diagnostics, complex program, health-improving physical culture.

Relevance. Preserving and strengthening the health of the population is one of the main strategic development tasks of any country. In Uzbekistan, it is regulated and provided by such regulatory

documents as the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (dated September 23, 2020, No. LRU-637), the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve and popularize physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" (dated January 24, 2020, No. DP-5924), as well as "On measures to widely introduce a healthy lifestyle and further develop mass sports" (dated October 30, 2020, No. DP-6099) aimed at ensuring the formation of a stable immune system against diseases in every citizen through regular physical education and mass sports and the formation of healthy lifestyle skills, rejection of bad habits, adherence to the principles of proper nutrition, systematic and effective organization of work on recovery and rehabilitation, mass events for physical activity, creation of appropriate infrastructure and other necessary conditions, etc. [1,2,3].

One of the problems of health promotion and physical development, in particular, of student youth is the unfavorable environmental situation both throughout the world and in our country. The scale of the ecological crisis and its tendencies rightly cause public and civil concern, as it affects the physical condition and health of the population [4,5,6].

This problem is of particular importance for student youth, whose health is sensitive to any environmental changes in the region. At the same time, it is not always possible to prevent the negative impact of adverse factors on the growing organism.

One of the problems of health promotion and physical development, in particular, of student youth is the unfavorable environmental situation both throughout the world and in our country. The scale of the ecological crisis and its tendencies rightly cause public and civil concern, as it affects the physical condition and health of the population.

According to N.A. Aghajanyan (1996), R.B. Abdullaev, M.S. Ruzmetova (2003), S.M. Omirbaeva (2004), E.S. Tatina and etc. (2014), B.G. Mukasheva (2015), this problem is of particular importance for student youth, whose health is sensitive to any environmental changes in the region. At the same time, it is not always possible to prevent the negative impact of adverse factors on the growing organism.

From the point of view of preserving the health of student youth, the effectiveness of traditional physical education classes in higher educational institutions does not meet the task. Research by A. Berdimuratova (1997), R. Kazakova (1997), I.A. Koshbakhtieva (2005), V.Sh. Rakhimov (2006) showed that the state of health of students for 4-6 years of study at the university deteriorates: problems arise with posture, excess weight, the state of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, the musculoskeletal system, and physical fitness indicators decrease (Y.I. Zvinyatskovsky, 1991; Sh.T. Iskandarova, 1998; B.A. Duschonov, 2000, etc.).

In connection with the above, some authors (A.A. Baranov, 1998; A.V. Anisimova, N.K. Perevoshchikova, 2013; M.G. Ishmukhametov, 2006; Y.D. Zheleznyak, 2006, etc.) to intensify the process of physical education and solving the existing problems, it is proposed to use selectively directed loads on various systems of the body. Along with this, it becomes especially important to search for ways to improve the health of student youth living in an area with an unfavorable environmental situation, to prevent and reduce the risk of ecologically caused pathological reactions (A.A. Baranov, 1998; R.I. Markhvaidze, 2000; Y.P. Gichev, 2002, etc.). For this it is necessary to adjust the concept of preserving, strengthening and shaping the health of young people. If until recently it was believed that the development of the disease can be prevented only by eliminating the negative factor of influence on the body, now it is more expedient to talk about such measures of influence, when using which the body itself optimizes

the work of its organs and systems, leveling the effect of the external environment and remaining healthy (S.I.Guskov, 1998; V.V. Markov, 2001; G.A. Gilev, 2006, etc.).

In connection with the above, a number of authors (L.B. Andryushenko, 2001; E.N. Weiner, 2001; V.M. Naskalov, 2004; L.P. Borisova, 2005; I.A. Koshbakhtiev et al., 2005; V. Sh. Rakhimov (2007) and others) recognize the existence of a scientific problem, which is characterized by the need to preserve, strengthen and form a high level of health of students by means of physical education and the lack of development of scientifically sound physical education and recreation technologies for students who constantly live in environmentally unfavorable environmental conditions.

Purpose of the research: the determination of methodological ways to optimize the process of physical development and fitness of female students with a predisposition to various diseases, using modern non-traditional types, means and methods of health related physical culture.

The tasks of research:

1. To determine the annual dynamics of physical development and readiness of female students living in ecologically unfavorable environmental conditions and having a predisposition to various diseases.
2. To develop a program based on the use of complexes of modern non-traditional types of health related physical culture, aimed at the development of physical qualities and improving the health level of female students and experimentally check its effectiveness.

The results of research and their discussion.

Preliminary and ascertaining experiment. At the beginning of the 2017-2018 academic year, at the Urgench State University (Uzbekistan, Khorezm region), more than 700 female students were examined by the method of computerized electro puncture diagnostics.

An analysis of domestic and foreign studies related to the determination of various properties of biologically active (reflexogenic) zones on the skin surface, using the method of computerized electro puncture diagnostics, indicates the possibility of obtaining diagnostic information from these zones. So, by changing the electrical parameters of biologically active zones, including the eclectic conductivity (the strength of the passing current), one can judge the localization of the pathological process, as well as its dynamics during the development of the disease or during treatment. In addition, it has been shown that these changes in these biologically active zones can appear earlier than clear clinical signs of the disease, that is identification of early stages of the disease is possible.

With the help of this technique, the confirmation of the results of the analysis of medical records of the examined students was obtained.

The analysis of the research results revealed 3 main groups predisposed to functional changes in the health status of female students: 1st group - cardiovascular system (CVS); 2nd Group - the respiratory system (RS); 3rd Group - musculoskeletal system (MS).

We present the results of indicators of physical and functional development during the preliminary and ascertaining experiment of three main groups of female students predisposed to various diseases during the 2017/2018 academic year. The average values of the functional indicators of the vital capacity of the lungs (VCL), the Ruffier-Dixon index (RDI), the Barbell and Gench tests in girls of three groups at the beginning of the school year were, respectively: in

the 1st group - 2.4 ± 0.6 l, $11, 1 \pm 0.7$, 28.3 ± 2.4 s and 18.8 ± 3.4 s, and at the end - 2.3 ± 0.6 L (P <0.05), $11.3 \pm 0, 8$ (P > 0.05), 27.8 ± 2.2 s (P <0.05) and 18.1 ± 3.2 s (P <0.01); in the 2nd - 2.2 ± 0.5 l, 10.9 ± 0.6 , 18.8 ± 2.2 s and 13.7 ± 2.9 s, and at the end - $2.0 \pm 0, 4$ L (P > 0.05), 11.1 ± 0.7 (P > 0.05), 18.1 ± 2.0 s (P <0.05) and 13.1 ± 2.6 s (P > 0.05); in 3rd group - 2.8 ± 0.5 l, 11.1 ± 1.1 , 31.3 ± 2.1 s and 20.7 ± 2.3 s, and at the end - $2.7 \pm 0, 7$ L (P > 0.01), 10.9 ± 1.2 (P > 0.05), 29.2 ± 2.7 s (P <0.01) and 18.8 ± 3.1 s (P <0.05).

To determine the level of physical fitness (FP) and public health, special tests "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" were used, developed by the Ministry of Physical Culture and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Public Education, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources, The Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Defense, the Council of the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan for girls and boys 18-23 years old.

The girls were tested according to the following program: running 100 m, running 2000 m, long jump from the spot, bending forward from a standing position to determine flexibility, lifting the trunk from a supine position, running-walking for 6 minutes, throwing a grenade.

The conducted pedagogical experiment showed that with traditional methods of physical education in universities among female students with a high risk of predisposition to various diseases, at the beginning and at the end of the academic year, most of the indicators of physical fitness and health in the dynamics did not have significant differences (P > 0.05) ... However, significant differences in dynamics at the beginning and at the end of the academic year had: indicators of the tests "long jump from the spot" and "throwing a grenade" in the group of female students with a risk of predisposition to cardiovascular diseases; indicators of the test "throwing a grenade" - only among female students with a risk of predisposition to diseases of the respiratory system; indicators of the test "long jump from a spot" - only among female students with a risk of predisposition to diseases of the musculoskeletal system (P <0.05).

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The main experiment. The main task after the preliminary and establishing experiment is to develop comprehensive programs based on the use of modern non-traditional types, means and methods of health physical culture, aimed at developing lagging physical qualities and improving the health status of students at Urgench State University.

When Using the method of computer electro puncture diagnostics, studies were re-conducted and the main diseases that are predisposed to university students were determined. These are diseases in the cardiovascular, respiratory and endocrine systems of the body, musculoskeletal system.

Based on the data obtained for the subsequent experiment, a main group of female students with a predisposition to diseases in the respiratory system was formed. The experimental group consisted of 30 girls.

The experiment analyzed the following:

- Structure and content of classes on modern non-traditional types of health physical education;
- The method of training the exercises of modern non-traditional types of health physical culture;
- control in classes.

According to the results of control tests, the level of physical development and fitness, as well as the state of health of students, was determined according to special tests of the "Barchinoy" complex.

It was assumed that the most effective is a complex that contains all types of exercises in the optimal ratio and a program that solves several tasks in one lesson, for each of the groups. This program is called complex. However, the authors' existing recommendations on the design and application of integrated programs need some refinement and correction in order to use them in practice in working with a specific contingent, namely, girls 18-23 years who are predisposed to changes in their state of health.

All of the above allowed:

- To select the means of modern non-traditional types of recreational physical culture, determine their sequence and distribute them into sections of education (according to increasing complexity); - for students who are predisposed to diseases in the respiratory system, to develop a comprehensive program on modern non-traditional types of recreational physical culture.

Based on the results of research by scientists and practitioners, as well as data on the assessment of the functional state of girls, their level of physical fitness, a comprehensive program on modern non-traditional types of health physical education for female students has been developed.

To solve this problem, the main experiment was conducted in the period of the 2018/2019 academic year at Urgench State University at the Department of General Physical Education.

Students of the experimental group were engaged in health physical education under developed comprehensive programs once a week for two hours in educational and independent physical education classes. During the period of the experiment, 72 educational and 52 hours of self-study physical education classes were held.

During the school year, physical education classes in the preparatory and final parts of the lesson used comprehensive respiratory gymnastics programs by A.N. Strelnikova in a group of students with a predisposition to illness in the respiratory system.

The main focus of the program on independent physical education classes is a comprehensive combination of modern species, such as basic and power aerobics, exercises for the development of physical qualities, as well as non-traditional and eastern types of health physical culture.

The training in the experimental group was conducted by qualified teachers with many years of experience in non-traditional types of health physical culture.

The selection of funds, the development of the program and the distribution of loads by semesters were carried out on the basis of an analysis of existing methods of classes with a healthy orientation in educational institutions; their accessibility to those engaged in various pedagogical observations that do not require complex equipment was taken into account.

A comprehensive program was developed for two semesters of the academic year (Fig. 1). In the first semester (retracting) on independent lessons, the means of basic aerobics and exercises for the development of physical qualities, as well as elements of exercises of non-traditional and oriental types of health-improving physical culture were used.

Fig. 1. Ratio of modern non-traditional types of health physical culture during the school year for female students with a predisposition to disease in the respiratory system.

In the II semester (training), self-study exercises in basic aerobics, which were also carried out in the preparatory part of the lesson, were used. The basis of the II semester was power types of aerobics, shape aerobics, as well as elements of exercises of non-traditional and eastern types of recreational physical culture.

Physical development is one of the leading indicators of the health status of female students. In this regard, many researchers believe that it is possible to judge human health by the level of physical development [12].

The results of indicators of physical and functional development during the experiment of a group of female students predisposed to diseases of the respiratory system are given in Table 1.

We can talk about the influence of a particular technique on the given indicators, however, it is known that their values are quite tightly controlled by the genome and are the most stable indicators of individual features of the body. Thus, the analysis of the dynamics of the main morphofunctional indicators of female students in the experimental group showed that the increase in body length averaged 0.5% per year ($P < 0.05$); no significant differences were found in body weight gain, in changes in shoulder and pelvic width, chest girth compared to baseline data in the group ($P > 0.05$). During the experiment, the students of this group showed changes in the indicators of the skin-fat layer (SFL). Thus, in the experimental group, unidirectional changes were found towards a decrease in the SFL of the shoulder behind, forearm, hip and tibia, respectively: by 10.4% ($P < 0.05$), 4.3% ($P > 0.05$), 8.2% ($P < 0.05$) and 5.8% ($P < 0.05$).

Table 1

Dynamics of morphofunctional indicators of the experimental group of students of Urgench State University

Indicators	September 2018		June 2019		Differences		t calc
	X	$\pm\delta$	X	$\pm\delta$	Δx	$\pm\Delta\delta$	

Body length	sm	154,5	4,3	155,2	4,6	0,7	0,30	2,33
Body weight	Kg	56,0	5,8	56,2	5,9	0,2	0,10	2,00
Girth of gr. Cells at rest	Sm	79,7	5,5	81,1	4,5	1,4	1,00	1,40
The width of shoulder	Sm	38,4	1,2	38,6	1,3	0,2	0,10	2,00
The width of Pelvic	Sm	44,6	1,4	44,8	1,5	0,2	0,10	2,00
The girth shoulder	Sm	23,4	2,1	24,2	1,8	0,8	0,30	2,67
The girth forearm	Sm	21,6	1,2	21,9	1,1	0,3	0,10	3,00
The girth hip	Sm	41,2	3,5	41,8	2,8	0,6	0,70	0,86
The girth shin	Sm	30,7	2,0	31,2	1,8	0,5	0,20	2,50
The SFL of the shoulder from behind	Mm	22,2	4,1	19,9	3,2	2,3	0,90	2,56
The SFL of forearm	Mm	13,8	2,1	13,2	1,8	0,6	0,30	2,00
The SFL of hip	Mm	34,2	5,7	31,4	4,7	2,8	1,00	2,80
The SFL of shingles	Mm	29,2	4,5	27,5	3,9	1,7	0,60	2,83
The systole	Arterial pressure	114,0	7,0	116,0	6,2	2,0	0,80	2,50
The diastole	Arterial pressure	74,0	6,0	75,0	5,5	1,0	0,50	2,00
LC	Liters	2,1	0,4	2,6	0,2	0,5	0,22	2,27
Heart rate	beats per minute	98,0	4,6	89,0	1,1	9,0	3,50	2,57
The RDI		11,3	0,8	9,8	0,3	1,5	0,54	2,77
The sample of Gench	Sec	14,1	3,5	18,5	1,8	3,4	1,70	2,59
The sample of Barbell	Sec	25,3	4,8	34,3	1,5	9,0	3,30	2,73
Flexibility	Sm	-12,0	6,9	-7,0	5,0	5,0	1,90	2,63

Note: at $t_{calc.} = 2.08$ $P < 0.05$

RDI is an indicator of the functional state of the cardiovascular system, and its value decreases as the adaptive capabilities of the circulatory system increase. An analysis of the rate of increase in the adaptive capabilities of the circulatory system showed that in students of the experimental

group, the increase in cardiovascular efficiency was 13.3%. Differences are statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

To determine the resistance to oxygen deficiency, functional breath-holding tests were used (barbell)

and breath-holding by exhalation (Gencha). The annual dynamics of barbell and Gench sample indicators indicate an increase in the resistance of the student body to hypoxia. An analysis of the rate of increase in the adaptive capabilities of the respiratory system showed that the students of the experimental group had an increase in the indicators of barbell and Gench samples of 26.2% and 23.8%, respectively. Differences are statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). According to the criteria for assessing the state of health (according to T.V. Volkova, A.G. Volkova (1986), in the experimental group of students, the DRI, Barbell and Gench samples at the end of the experiment correspond to the "good" assessment. Thus, the functionality of the circulatory system and the mechanisms for adapting the body of students of the experimental group to hypoxia conditions function quite reliably in adverse environmental conditions when using modern non-traditional types and means of health physical culture in physical education classes compared to similar indicators of students engaged in the traditional method of physical education at the university. Indicators of PF of students of experimental group before and after pedagogical experiment are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Dynamics of physical fitness of the experimental group students of Urgench State University

Indicators		September		June		Differences		t calc
		2018		2019				
		X	$\pm\delta$	X	$\pm\delta$	Δx	$\pm\Delta\delta$	
Run 100m	m/s	19,1	1,2	18,0	0,7	1,1	0,45	2,44
Cross 2000m	min/s	15,32	0,9	13,53	0,3	1,4	0,56	2,48
Jump in long. from place	sm	155,3	1,2	166,0	5,4	10,7	4,20	2,55
Raise the torso from the floor. lying down	number/ time	16,0	5,3	24,0	2,1	8,0	3,20	2,50
athletic walking 6 min	M	860,5	21,6	948,7	68,1	88,2	46,50	1,90
Throwing 500g grenades	M	17,0	1,8	20,1	0,6	3,1	1,20	2,41

Note: at $t_{calc.} = 2.08$ $P < 0.05$

A comparative analysis of the PF indicators of the students of the experimental group showed that at the end of the experiment there were changes in almost all three groups: running at 100 m - the improvement was 5.8% ($P < 0.05$); cross for 2000 m - the improvement was on average

1.39 min/s ($P < 0.05$); long jump from place - improvement revealed by 6.4% ($P < 0.05$); body lifting from lying down position - improvement revealed by 33.2% ($P < 0.05$); running-walking 6 min - improvement revealed by 9.3% ($P > 0.05$); grenade throwing - improvement revealed by 15.4% ($P < 0.05$).

After training under the comprehensive program on physical education developed by us, the number of students of the experimental group who completed the standards of special tests of the "Barchinoy" complex amounted to 42%.

Thus, the pedagogical experiment conducted showed that the use of modern non-traditional types and means of health physical culture in educational and independent classes allows you to significantly increase the level of AF of students living in unfavorable environmental conditions and having a predisposition to diseases of the respiratory system [13].

At the end of the school year, a re-examination of female students predisposed to respiratory system diseases was carried out with the help of computer electric point diagnostics.

An analysis of the results of the survey revealed that the students of the experimental group, predisposed to functional changes in the state of health, had improved their physical condition. Thus, Fig.2 shows changes of biologically active zones towards improvement.

Fig. 2. Indicators of the state of functional systems of students of the experimental group (after the experiment).

Functional changes in experimental groups make it possible to state the fact that parameters characterizing the activities of the heart and vessels (S7, IG4, TR4, G15), AH organs (R9, MC7), as well as the musculoskeletal system (RP3, F3, R5, U65) have adopted proper health standards.

Conclusion. Theoretical understanding of the problem and experimental work made it possible to formulate the following conclusions and recommendations:

3. The analysis of scientific and methodological literature showed that until now the technology of differentiated physical development and preparedness has not been developed in higher educational institutions for female students with a predisposition to diseases. The development of technologies for student physical education software with a healthy orientation will allow to solve with the greatest efficiency the problems of preparing student youth for work and social activities in environmentally unfavorable environmental conditions.

4. With traditional methods of physical education in universities among female students with a high risk of predisposition to various diseases, at the beginning and at the end of the academic year, most of the indicators of physical fitness and health in the dynamics did not have significant differences ($P > 0.05$). However, there were significant differences in the dynamics at the beginning and end of the academic year: indicators of the tests "long jump from the spot" and "throwing a grenade" in the group of female students with a risk of predisposition to cardiovascular diseases; indicators of the test "throwing a grenade" - only among female students at risk of predisposition to respiratory system diseases; indicators of the long jump test - only among female students with a risk of predisposition to diseases of the musculoskeletal system ($P < 0.05$) ...
5. The use of traditional physical education classes in combination with modern non-traditional types and means of health physical education in educational and independent classes of students of the experimental group contributed to a reliable ($P < 0.05$) improvement in the indicators of physical fitness in running 100 m, 2000 m, long jump from a place, lifting the body from a lying position and throwing a grenade.
6. After training under the comprehensive program on physical education developed by us, the number of students of the experimental group who completed the standards of special tests of the "Barchinoy" complex increased by 27%. The level of health of students of this group according to the Ruffier-Dixon index, barbell and Gench samples after applying the developed comprehensive program on physical education corresponded to the "good" assessment.
7. The complex program developed and proposed by us, combining traditional and non-traditional means of health-improving physical culture, makes it possible to differentiate approaches to physical education and contributes to an increase in the level of physical fitness, physical and functional development, as well as health indicators of female students who have a risk of predisposition to the development of diseases of the respiratory system ...

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